

EXPLORING THE ROLE OF ISLAMIC EDUCATION IN MITIGATING INDISCIPLINE AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN IBADAN NORTH LOCAL GOVERNMENT OF OYO STATE**GANIYU, Mojeed Ademola***Department of Islamic Studies**School of Secondary Education**(Arts & Social Sciences)**Oyo State College of Education**Lanlate, Oyo State***Abstract**

The study aims at investigating the factors that are contributing to indiscipline among secondary schools in Ibadan North Local Government Area of Oyo State. The descriptive Survey method was adopted for the study. The methodology involved a sample of three (300) respondents, one hundred and sixty (160) students and one hundred and forty (140) teachers selected from ten schools used for the study. The instrument used was the questionnaire (QFTOFTIASS) and (QFSOFTIASS) for the teachers and students respectively. These research questions and hypotheses were tested through the use of questionnaire of two forms. The results revealed that significant relationship exist between students' family background, school authority, peer groups, government's influence and acts of indiscipline on the part of students. The data therefore support the hypothesis of relationship in the students' acts of indiscipline with the afore mentioned independent variables. The writer idealize the Islamic teachings contain in the Holy Qura'an and Hadith in solving the menace of indiscipline and reform their moral discipline, thus we have the standard discipline, thus we have the standard discipline among our students in our schools in particular and the society in general. The writer is of the opinion that in the effort to instill discipline and minimize indiscipline problem in schools, the society, teachers and parents should join hands to make sure the challenge of indiscipline is reduced to the barest minimum. Moreover, it is suggested that the Government at all levels should allow the teaching of religious education (Islamic and Christian education) in our secondary schools for moral behaviour in the sense that fear of God is the beginning of wisdom.

Keywords: Indiscipline, Students, Mitigating, Islamic Education, Panacea.**Introduction**

The increasing rate of indiscipline among Nigerian Students in recent years has given the Government, Education Authorities as well as patriotic citizens much concern. Most especially, for the past one or two decades, no year passed without publication and sensational stories relating to students' indiscipline in the Nigerian newspaper. Considering what the future may hold for the country in the hands of the expected leaders of tomorrow, one may not be astonished to see the several efforts of Nigerian government and educational authorities in finding

solutions to the rampant acts of indiscipline in Nigerian schools in particular and among the people in the society in general. Their efforts include the following:

- a. Introduction of corporal punishment into Nigerian secondary schools between 1976 and 1979.
- b. Launching of War Against Indiscipline (WAI) both in private and public places in 1976.
- c. Organization of seminar or workshops on indiscipline in schools.

- d. Setting up investigating panels on the causes of students' indiscipline with a view of finding solutions to it.

Unfortunately, with all these steps taken by the Governments, all these efforts proved futile. Instead, this unruly behaviour, indiscipline among the school students who are pegged to be the leaders of tomorrow keeps increasing. The attempt to eradicate this act of indiscipline amongst our secondary school students remains the main focus of the researcher in this paper.

Literature Review

According to Macmillan English Dictionary for Advanced Learner (2005), the concept of discipline is summarized as the practice of making people obey rules of behaviour and punishing them if they do not. Also, Aka (1985) defines discipline as the training or move of life in accordance with the rule; subjection to control; order. Through the above definition of the term discipline, it is understood that indiscipline means lack of discipline, control and proper training. It also means unruly behaviour, disobedience, disorder etc, which are the order of the day presently in the nation. It should be noted that national transformation is impossible in the absence of discipline, morality, sincerity, hardwork and God consciousness.

Types of Indiscipline

Adesina (1980) identifies four types of indiscipline commonly found in the school system as indiscipline relating to the habit of individual, disregard for school regulations, disrespect to the school authorities and collective misbehavior of the student group. According to Idris (1984), indiscipline in schools takes different forms, stealing, dishonest, sex offences, disobedience, assault, truancy assault and insult.

Causes of Indiscipline

According to Alao (1998), six major causes of indiscipline in secondary schools are as follows: home adjustment problems, social problems, health problems, psychological problems and vocational problems. He went further to say that boys adjust more easily than girls in problems, while junior students feel insecure in relationship to demand in

social interaction. Aderounmu and Ehiamentalor (1981) were of the opinion that indiscipline is due to many factors. These, according to them, are usually external to school though may stem from problems within such as lack of dedication to duty on the part of teachers, ambiguous rules and non-involvement in school affairs.

In his work, Olowa (1989) identified the inability to plan for and meet the challenges that are passed by social changes as one among the many causes of indiscipline in schools. Other causes identified by him are lack of adequate provision of social welfare services, lack of good leadership, imbalance in student teacher ratio in schools, ineffective co-ordination between the school and the home. From the above, one can deduce that indiscipline in schools as well as in the society is not without causes. However, the relevance of the reasons advanced and their acceptability still have to be further researched into by scholars.

Peer Group Influence

According to Alao (1998), peer group, an agent of socialization ignites indiscipline amongst students. To him, peer group serves an all important reference group because they learn from one another. Sometimes, the behavior and value of peer groups may be positive or negative. As a result of this, the child may be influenced by certain actions or character which otherwise influences him or her in a negative way. In view of this, parents are advised to control their children from moving with bad groups. An adage says 'Bad company ruins good morals'.

Effect of Students' Indiscipline

Adeshina and Obanya (1981) argued that indiscipline will make the job of administrators to be more complex because the needs of the students will become more varied, since there will be a need to develop a cadre of staffs who specialize in various aspect of students' services such as guidance and counselors, nurses, visiting doctors, psychiatrists, etc. However, according to Alao (1998), undisciplined behaviour of students has led to rampant exposition of our youths to social ills such as armed robbery, cyber-criminals and drug abuse. Therefore, these have to be eradicated to have a just and free

society, since all these immoral acts in effect leads to the poor academic performance of students.

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher used the descriptive survey method which describes the variable employed in the implementation of this study. It aimed at investigating the factors contributing to acts of indiscipline among students in some selected schools in Ibadan North Local Government Area of Oyo State.

Variable Research

This study comprises the following variables (dependent, students' indiscipline), independent (factors affecting indiscipline) such as family background, teacher, peer group, society moderating variables such as age, sex.

Population

The population of this study comprises 930 teachers and 23,200 students from twenty nine (29) secondary schools in Ibadan North Local Government Area of Oyo State.

Sample and Sampling Technique

One hundred and forty (140) teachers and One hundred and sixty (160) students were randomly sampled from the population through stratified method.

Instrumentation

The research instrument for this study was a structured questionnaire of forty items grouped into twenty items, each for students and teachers respectively. The questionnaire for teachers is coded (OFTOFTIASS) and that of students is titled (OFSOFTIASS). They were all based on 5 likert-rating scale starting from Strongly Agreed (SA) to Strongly Disagreed (SD).

Validation

The questionnaire was scrutinized revised and approved by two experts in Educational

Management Department of University of Ibadan

Reliability

Test re-test method was used to determine the reliability of the questionnaire in which some questionnaire were given to a number of respondents and these questionnaires were re-administered to the respondents some days after the collection of the first response.

Procedure for Data-Collection

Structured questionnaire were personally distributed to the respondents. The respondents were assured of the research confidentially five day were given them complete before they were collected.

Data Analysis

In order to analyze the collected data, the researcher made use of Kendal correction co-efficient on hypothesis 1 (one).

H₀₁: There is no correlation between family background and students' indiscipline in secondary schools.

ITEM II of QFSOFTIASS and items 10 of QFTUFTIASS questionnaires were used to treat the hypothesis using Kendal. The result is 0.3. This shows that there is low level of concordance among the respondents behaviour. Hence, H₀ (NU II hypothesis) is rejected. That means there is correlation between family background and students' discipline in secondary schools.

H₀₂ (Hypothesis 2): There is no significant relationship between the school management style and the acts of indiscipline of secondary school students.

To properly analyze this hypothesis, items 9 and 10 of QFTUFTIASS respectively were used.

Result of T-TEST comparing the difference in the analyzed factors contributing to indiscipline among secondary school students

VARIABLE	N	EX	X	VARIANCE	T. OBSERVED	I.C.	P
STUDENTS	160	4006	50.28	43.19	0.16	2	0.05
TEACHER	140	3011	50.28	37.04			

Source: Field Survey
 DF = 300-2=298
 t = Critical = 2.00
 t = Observed = 0.16
 t = Observed is less than t-critical
 H₀₂ Null hypothesis is rejected.

Therefore, there is significant relationship between the school management weakness and the Students’ Indiscipline in Secondary Schools.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between the peer group influence and the bad behaviour of Secondary School Students.

VARIABLE	N	X	X	X ²	VARIANCE	(SD)	T. OBSERVED	CRITICAL
STUDENTS	160	1153	52.4	607.66	29	5.38	3.16	2.00
TEACHERS	140	858	47.66	15.33	3.19			

Source: Field Survey
 D1 = 300-298
 T = Critical Level = 2.00
 t = Observed = 3.16

Interference (Result): Since t-observed is 3.16 and t-critical are 2.00. H₀ is rejected. The table above shows that the calculated t-value which is greater than the critical value. To this regard, the Null hypothesis is rejected, hence, there is significant relationship between the peer group influence and secondary schools students’ bad behaviour.

Summary of Findings

The results of the following findings are summed up as follows:

- There is correlation (or agreements) between family, background and secondary school students’ misbehavior.
- There is significant relationship between the school authority management style and the indiscipline acts of secondary schools students.
- There is significant relationship between the peer group influence and acts of indiscipline of secondary

schools students in Ibadan North Local Government Area of Oyo State.

Islamic Moral Education as Panacea to the Acts of Indiscipline

In Islam, the practice of good conduct is not of personal philosophy or native customs. Allah is the maker of man, so He knows what is good for him. He knows what man can do and those that he must not do in order to attain peace. Therefore, good moral conduct for a Muslim depends on the commandments of Allah and the teaching of Prophet Muhammed (SAW).

The following are among the moral codes from the Quran: obedience to parents,

cleanness, telling the truth and keeping promises. They also include preventing stealing, corruption, cheating and modesty and humility.

The Holy Quran warns us against disobedience and committing acts of indiscipline mentioned earlier in this work, which are menace to the development and healthy living in our schools and society. The Almighty Allah commands us to be dutiful to our parents and the elderly people and be disciplined in the following Quranic verses: And your Lord has decree that:

You worship none but Him and that you should be kind and obey your parents, if one of them or both of them attain the old age in your life say not to them a word of disrespect nor shout at them but address them un terms of honour. And however unto them the using of submission and humility through mercy as they did bring me up when I was young.

Quran 17:23-24

The above verses of the Quran condemn the act of indiscipline. They prohibit disobedience to parents, the elderly people, teachers, with the recommendation to be humble when dealing with everyone. On the acts of indiscipline in our society it says:

Verily, Allah enjoins Al-Adl (Justice) and Ihsan (good work) and forbids Al-fasah (all evil deeds e.g. illegal sexual acts, disobedience and indiscipline)

Quran 16:90

Regarding adultery which has become rampant in both schools and the society at large, the Almighty Allah warns against that act of indiscipline in these words:

And come not near to unlawful sexual intercourse, verily it is a fansahi i.e. a great.

Quran 17:32-33

It is also an act of indiscipline to be dishonest. This Almighty Allah warns us against in the Holy Quran thus:

O you who believe neither betray not Allah and His messenger nor betray knowingly your Amanah things entrusted to you and all you duties which Allah has ordained for you.

Quran 81:27

Among the acts of indiscipline are embezzlement and corruption which have become the menace affecting economy in Nigeria and causing serious hunger in our society. Almighty Allah has prohibited it Holy Quran when He commands against its practice thus:

And eat not one another's property unjustly (in any illegal way (before presenting your case), that you may knowingly eat up the part of the property of others sinfully.

Quran 2:18

Base on this, the students in our secondary schools of nowadays should be respectful to the school authority, their teachers and Senior. As Allah commands them to be doing in the verse of the Holy Quran:

O you who believe, obey Allah and obey the apostle of Allah and those who are placed in authority among you.

Quran 4:39

Recommendation

This work has revealed the laying a good example for the younger people will help to reduce the acts of indiscipline in secondary schools.

- Based on this administration of the secondary schools should ensure participation of parents in matters involving discipline. This will enable the schools and the home to work cooperatively in handling disciplinary problems of the schools.
- The Government should ensure that schools are adequately staffed in order to enable students get maximum benefits from their stay in the institutions.
- Moreover, the Government should allow the teaching of religious

doctrines (Islamic and Christian education) in our secondary schools so as to inculcate moral behaviour into the students.

- In addition, the Government should uplift teaching profession by increasing teachers' salaries and other benefits and at the same time pay their salaries as at when due. There should be adequate facilities in schools to facilitate effective teaching and learning processes.
- Education should be a right and not a privilege, the Government should make Education be free at all levels so that the less privileged ones will have opportunity of going to school.
- In order to reduce and minimize disciplinary problems in schools, the society as a whole should work hand in hand to make sure the challenge of indiscipline is eradicated to a barest minimum.

Conclusion

Some conclusions are drawn from the findings. The researchers on the basis of analyzed responses and discussion have come out with the following conclusion as regards factors contributing to indiscipline in secondary schools. It had been observed that in Nigeria today, much emphasis is placed on having more secondary schools without equipping them adequately. Besides, home background of students caused indiscipline in secondary schools. Some parents pay little or no attention to their children in the sense that they place greater priority on money at the expenses of their wards. They have been the causes of their children's lateness to school in the sense that such parent may be lazy at home work and expect their children to do everything before going to school. Some parents are too careless and over indulge their children at home. Inadequate staff also causes indiscipline among the students. In addition to this, some teachers in the secondary schools show bad examples to students through their dressing and behaviours.

References

- Aderounmu, W.O. & Ehiamentor, E.T. (1981). Introduction to administration of schools in Nigeria. PGDE-113 pdf. Ibadan. University of Ibadan.
- Adesina, S.A & Obasanya, M.O. (1981), Indiscipline in Nigerian education and Nigerian Society. Ibadan: University Press Limited.
- Adesina, S.A. (1980). School discipline in some aspects of school management. Ilorin. University of Ilorin Press.
- Aka, S.M.O. (1985): Model essays and letters. Benin City, Nigeria: S.M.O. Aka and Brothers.
- Alao, S.A. (1998). An investigating study on some of the causes of indiscipline behaviour among students in Ogbomoso South Local Government Area of Oyo State; A Long Essay Submitted to the Institute of Education, University of Ibadan.
- Ali, A.Y. (1998). The Holy Quran: Text, translation and commentary. Beirut: Lebanon, Daral-Arabia.
- Hornby, H.S. (200). Oxford advanced learners dictionary. Oxford University Press. England.
- Idris, O.W. (1984). Indiscipline in schools: Causes and remedy in National Concord 18th March, Page 5.
- Olowu, S.A. (1982). Juvenile delinquency: causes and remedy in Nigerian Herald of September 8th, 1982, Page 4.
- Rokosu, A.M. (1984). War against indiscipline, Lagos: Lagos State Government Press Release Booklet for the Month October, 1984.

